

Stability Constants of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Fe(II) and Zn(II) Complexes with 8-Formyl-7-Hydroxy-4-Methyl-2H-1-Benzopyran-2-one

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Manuscript received 7 November 1981, revised 25 June 1982, accepted 28 December 1982

Proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants of 8-formyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (FHMB) complexes with Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Fe(II) and Zn(II) were determined pH-metrically in 50% v/v methanol-water at 30° and a constant ionic strength of 0.1 M NaClO₄ using the Irving and Rossotti titration technique. The order of stability constants (log β₁), Fe(II) > Cu(II) > Ni(II) > Zn(II) > Co(II) was in conformity with Irving-Williams order except in the case of Fe(II). The abnormally high stability of Fe(II) system is attributed to the resonance stabilisation energy derived through the coordination with ligands of aromatic ring system.

COUMARINS. (2H-1-benzopyran-2-one), are known for their physiological and fluorescent properties. A survey of literature revealed that studies on metal chelates of formyl coumarins have not been reported. The present study was taken up to examine the nature of interaction of some transition metal ions with 8-formyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (FHMB). pH-titration technique of Irving-Rossotti¹ was used to determine the proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants in 50% v/v methanol-water mixture at 30 ± 0.1 and μ = 0.1 M (NaClO₄).

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A. R. grade. Metal perchlorate solutions were standardised by known methods². The ligand FHMB was prepared by literature procedure³. The purity of the recrystallised sample was checked by tlc and m.m.p. A standard solution of the ligand (0.01 M) was prepared in methanol (spectroscopic grade).

The following mixtures were titrated against standard carbonate free NaOH solution (0.05 M) in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen: (i) 5 × 10⁻³ M HClO₄ (acid titration), (ii) 5 × 10⁻³ M HClO₄ + 2 × 10⁻³ M ligand solution (ligand titration), (iii) 5 × 10⁻³ M HClO₄ + 2 × 10⁻³ M ligand solution + 4 × 10⁻⁴ M metal ion solution (metal titration). An appropriate quantity of 1 M NaClO₄ solution was added to each of the above mixtures to maintain a constant ionic strength at 0.1 M. The total volume of each of the mixtures was made upto 50 ml such that solutions were 50% v/v in methanol-water. The pH was recorded with an Elico digital pH meter, model LI-120 equipped with a glass-calomel electrode assembly. The electrode system was calibrated with suitable buffers with necessary temperature corrections. The pH meter readings (B) in 50% v/v

methanol-water were corrected by the method suggested by Van Uitert and Haas⁴.

Results and Discussion

The values of $\bar{n}_H$, $\bar{n}$ and pL were calculated by the method of Irving and Rossotti¹ with necessary volume corrections.

From the proton-ligand formation curve the value of proton-ligand stability constant log K₁^H (corresponding to phenolic OH group) was obtained as Bjerrum's half-integral value. The same was also evaluated by other computational methods⁵ like point-wise calculation and linear plot. The values are consistent with each other.

The maximum $\bar{n}$ values calculated for each metal-ligand system were found to be not exceeding one, indicating the formation of 1:1 complex. The $\bar{n}$ calculations could not however be continued due to precipitation. To confirm that only a 1:1 complex is formed, it was checked by the following equation due to Irving and Rossotti⁶, as used by Ramamurthy and Santappa⁶.

$$\frac{\bar{n}}{(1-\bar{n}) [L]} = \beta_1 + \beta_2 \frac{(2-\bar{n}) [L]}{(1-\bar{n})}$$

Plots of $\bar{n}/(1-\bar{n}) [L]$ (=Y) vs $(2-\bar{n}) [L]/(1-\bar{n})$ (=X) were found to be good straight lines with definite slope instead of being parallel to the abscissa indicating the formation of both 1:1 and 1:2 metal-ligand complexes. As a representative case, the Zn(II), Co(II) and Ni(II) systems along with H⁺ system is indicated in Fig. 1. Therefore, the values of log K₁ and log K₂ were calculated using the least square treatment⁵. Values thus obtained along with log K₁^H are given in Table 1. The small differences between log K₁ and log K₂ values suggest that the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes occur with equal ease.

Fig. 1.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF FHMB IN 50% v/v METHANOL-WATER AT 30° AND $\mu = 0.1 M$ (NaClO₄)

Cation	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂
H	6.95	—	—
Cu(II)	5.66	4.54	10.20
Ni(II)	4.69	3.49	8.18
Co(II)	3.65	3.33	6.98
Fe(II)	6.51	5.12	11.63
Zn(II)	3.93	3.24	7.17

A comparison of log β₂ values reveals the following order of metal chelate stabilities: Fe(II) > Cu(II) > Ni(II) > Zn(II) > Co(II) which is in conformity with Irving-Williams order⁷ except in the case

of Fe(II). The abnormally high stability of Fe(II) chelate may be due to the resonance stabilisation energy derived through the coordination with ligands having aromatic ring system⁷.

Thus, FHMB acts as a monoprotic bidentate ligand coordinating through the oxygens of phenolic and formyl groups. Other studies relating to the isolation of solid metal complexes and also the possible use of this ligand as analytical reagent are in progress.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (K.J.C.) is grateful to New Science College, Ameerpet, Hyderabad and the other (K.L.O.P.) to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of Senior Research Fellowship.

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